

SafeHabitus

Deliverable 5.2

**Enabling conditions for market
developments supporting ethical
working conditions. A systematic
evaluation of CSR design and
implementation in the horticulture
sector**

Deliverable description

Deliverable	Enabling conditions for market developments supporting ethical working conditions. A systematic evaluation of CSR design and implementation in the horticulture sector Corporate Social Responsibility and Human Rights Due Diligence in the Huelva–Germany and Morocco–United Kingdom Strawberry Value Chains
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Acronyms and abbreviations

BHR: Business and Human Rights

BSCI: Business Social Compliance Initiative

CSDDD: Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive

CSR: Corporate Social Responsibility

ETI: Ethical Trade Initiative

EU: European Union

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

GECCO: Gestión Colectiva de Contrataciones en Origen (Collective Management of Hiring in Origin)

GRASP: GLOBALG.A.P. Risk Assessment on Social Practice

GVC: Global Value Chain

HRDD: Human Rights Due Diligence

HREDD: Human Rights and Environmental Due Diligence

ILO: International Labour Organization

KPI: Key Performance Indicator

LEAF: Linking Environment And Farming

LkSG: German Supply Chain Due Diligence Act

MSA: UK Modern Slavery Act 2015

NGO: Non-Governmental Organisation

OECD: Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

OHS: Occupational Health and Safety

Sedex: Supplier Ethical Data Exchange

SMETA: Sedex Members Ethical Trade Audit

UK: United Kingdom

UNDP: United Nations Development Programme

UNGP: UN Guiding Principles

Executive Summary

This report, produced as Deliverable 5.2 of the SafeHabitus project, analyses the design and implementation of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and human rights due diligence (HRDD)¹ frameworks in supermarket-led strawberry value chains supplying European markets. It assesses how these frameworks shape working conditions, occupational health and safety (OHS) and the vulnerability of migrant and seasonal agricultural workers. The research responds to Task 5.3 of Work Package 5, which applies a Farm to Fork perspective to understand the enabling conditions for market developments that support ethical working conditions.

Research design and methods

The study adopts a comparative case study design, examining two value chains: the Huelva-Germany strawberry chain, governed by a binding due diligence regime under the German Supply Chain Due Diligence Act (LkSG), and the Morocco-United Kingdom strawberry chain, embedded in a transparency-based model under the United Kingdom (UK) Modern Slavery Act. The research combines documentary analysis of CSR and HRDD policies, modern slavery and human rights statements, supplier codes of conduct and governance arrangements from twelve supermarkets (seven in the UK and five in Germany) with qualitative fieldwork comprising fourteen semi-structured interviews and one focus group. Interviews were conducted with independent experts, suppliers, importers and producers in both chains, while the focus group brought together representatives from five UK supermarkets.

Fieldwork was carried out in Huelva and in the Gharb-Loukkos region in north-western Morocco. Fieldwork in Morocco took place in July 2025. The Gharb-Loukkos region was selected following preparatory discussions with experts due to its relevance for strawberry agro-industry dynamics and its links to GECCO recruitment and migration networks connected to southern Spain.

Key findings

The analysis reveals that CSR and HRDD architectures have become increasingly sophisticated at corporate level, with formal commitments to international human rights standards, structured risk management procedures and audit-based verification systems.

¹ Throughout this report we use the term *human rights due diligence* (HRDD) rather than *human rights and environmental due diligence* (HREDD). This choice reflects the scope of the empirical research, which focuses on labour and other social human rights impacts in supermarket strawberry value chains. Environmental due diligence obligations, while highly relevant, fall outside the analytical framework of this study and are therefore not examined in a systematic way.

Supermarkets in both chains have developed governance structures that place accountability at senior levels, supported by supplier codes of conduct, social audit programmes and, in some cases, dedicated human rights impact assessments. However, the research finds that these instruments have only partially translated into substantive improvements in work organisation, wage practices, housing conditions, OHS or workers' effective capacity to claim their rights.

In the Huelva-Germany chain, the binding due diligence framework has driven greater formalisation of risk management systems and more detailed mapping of supplier risks, including those associated with seasonal work and employer-provided accommodation. One supermarket has conducted a specific human rights impact assessment for the Huelva chain, leading to an action plan addressing housing, worker voice and purchasing practices. Nevertheless, stakeholders across the chain describe a compliance culture focused on documentation and passing audits rather than on securing lasting improvements in labour conditions.

In the Morocco-United Kingdom chain, supermarkets have developed sophisticated collaborative tools, including multi-stakeholder platforms, 'beyond audit' approaches such as worker voice technologies, and rapid response mechanisms following media or non-governmental organisation (NGO) allegations. However, the transparency-based regulatory model provides weaker enforcement than binding due diligence, and the research documents significant gaps between formal commitments and conditions on farms. Stakeholders report that audits are routinely staged, with farms prepared in advance and sensitive issues concealed from inspectors.

Across both chains, commercial logics based on low prices, strict appearance standards and just-in-time sourcing continue to shift costs and risks onto producers and, in cascade, onto migrant and seasonal workers. Purchasing practices (including last-minute orders, rigid delivery windows, rejection clauses with little cost for the buyer, and delayed payments) create strong incentives for the labour intensification and cost-cutting. When these incentives dominate, CSR and HRDD-related measures may be discouraged, postponed, or implemented selectively, which limits their practical effectiveness. The distribution of power and value appears asymmetric: supermarkets set requirements, certifications and calendars, while producers bear the bulk of commercial risk and compliance costs.

The vulnerability of migrant and seasonal workers emerges as a structural feature common to both chains. Workers face high dependence on employers for housing and transport, intense work rhythms during peak season, limited possibilities for collective organisation and significant barriers to using grievance mechanisms without fear of reprisals. In Morocco, widespread informality persists, particularly among women workers, while in Huelva, gaps

remain between formal documentation and real working hours, with subcontracting and unstable seasonal employment limiting effective protection.

Comparative assessment

The benchmarking exercise classifies, for each chain, the level of residual social risk that remains after existing CSR and HRDD measures and applicable regulation have been taken into account. Residual risk is assessed across nine dimensions, including auditing and compliance, purchasing practices, labour formalisation, OHS, reputational dynamics, worker vulnerability and the distribution of power and value. The Huelva-Germany chain shows relatively lower risk in labour formalisation and regulatory anchoring, benefiting from a stronger legal framework and chain-specific interventions. The Morocco-United Kingdom chain demonstrates relative strengths in reputational dynamics and collaborative tools, but higher risk in labour formalisation, OHS and worker vulnerability due to the prevalence of informal employment and the limitations of a transparency-only regulatory model. Both chains show high residual risk in purchasing practices and the distribution of power and value, reflecting structural bottlenecks that CSR and HRDD frameworks have not addressed.

Recommendations

Based on the evidence produced, the report proposes recommendations to supermarkets and to the European Union (EU). Supermarkets should ensure strict respect for labour and human rights throughout their supply chains, pay fair prices that reflect the real costs of sustainable production and decent work, integrate human rights into corporate management and internal incentive systems, increase transparency and accountability by publishing supplier information and risk data, and orient purchasing policies toward supporting regional, organic and small-scale farming. The EU should develop and improve binding rules for responsible business conduct in order to build a legal framework that has a broad scope and strong enforcement, guarantees access to legal protection and remedies for affected persons, requires companies to adapt sourcing and purchasing policies to support decent work, and mandates the payment of living wages from the base of agricultural supply chains. The recent revision of the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD) is a missed opportunity in that regard, as it negatively affected key elements for effective legislation. This should be remediated in future reviews and addressed by complementary legislation. Meanwhile, member states should transpose the CSDDD in a way that closes gaps and ensures the effectiveness of the legislation.

Contribution to SafeHabitus

The findings contribute to all four Expected Outcomes of the SafeHabitus project: enhancing understanding of OHS challenges among policymakers and stakeholders; informing

improved policy and governance frameworks; identifying transferable CSR innovations for farm businesses; and providing evidence to support improved health, safety and labour conditions through better regulation and bottom-up initiatives. The research informs subsequent activities within Work Package 5, including Task 5.4 on mobile worker experiences and Task 5.5 on ethical trade governance structures, and will be presented at the Work Package 6 Policy Seminar on 27 January 2026.

Keywords

Strawberry value chains; supermarket-led supply chains; corporate social responsibility; human rights due diligence; migrant and seasonal agricultural workers; occupational health and safety.

Introduction

Supermarkets have become central actors in contemporary food systems, particularly in fresh produce markets. Their commercial strategies, quality specifications and private standards give them considerable coordinating power over geographically dispersed networks of producers and suppliers. In soft fruit chains such as strawberries, which are highly perishable and closely associated with retail competition around quality and price, this buyer driven governance model generates strong economic and logistical pressures along the entire chain.

At the same time, these chains rely heavily on migrant and seasonal workers, whose employment conditions are often characterised by intense work rhythms, low wages, variable working hours and strong dependence on employers for access to housing and transport. Evidence from different European agricultural contexts has documented recurrent patterns of informality, occupational risks and barriers to the exercise of rights, especially among women workers and migrant workers. These dynamics have raised questions about the capacity of existing CSR and HRDD instruments to deliver decent work outcomes in export-oriented agriculture.

Over the past decade, the regulatory landscape governing corporate responsibility in supply chains has undergone a significant transformation. The first EU country to pass binding regulation on the matter was France, with its 2017 Duty of Vigilance Law, which required companies to establish and implement a coherent plan with measures to prevent environmental and human rights violations throughout their supply chains. Various national legal frameworks have been developed since, such as Germany's LkSG (2021), which this report examines in more detail. Altogether with the regional instrument of the EU CSDDD (2024), they mark a shift from predominantly voluntary CSR towards binding HRDD obligations for large companies, including major supermarket chains. These regimes require companies to establish risk management systems, assess human rights and environmental risks, implement preventive and remedial measures and report on their efforts across their value chains. In parallel, transparency-based frameworks such as the UK Modern Slavery Act (2015) (MSA) have focused on disclosure obligations rather than enforceable due diligence steps, relying mainly on reputational incentives and public scrutiny.

In supermarket driven strawberry chains, these developments have led to the proliferation of human rights statements, supplier codes of conduct, social audit programmes and related tools. Supermarkets increasingly claim alignment with international human rights standards, integrate social risks into their enterprise risk registers and expand audit coverage of agricultural suppliers. However, empirical research suggests that the existence of these instruments does not automatically translate into substantive changes in labour practices on farms, the regulation of working time and wages, housing quality or workers capacity to

use grievance mechanisms without fear of reprisals. Empirical research and stakeholders in this study suggest that, in many cases, CSR and HRDD frameworks may operate primarily as reputational risk management and documentary compliance systems rather than as vehicles for redistributing power and value or reconfiguring purchasing practices.

This report offers a comparative analysis of two supermarket-led strawberry value chains, specifically one linking production in Huelva with distribution in Germany and another connecting production in Morocco with distribution in the UK, which makes it possible to observe how different regulatory models interact with private CSR and HRDD frameworks and how these influence working conditions and OHS on farms. It is situated at the intersection of three fields: the literature on CSR and HRDD in agrifood value chains, research on global value chains and food systems, and frameworks on the vulnerability of migrant and mobile workers. Empirically, it combines documentary analysis of CSR and HRDD policies, modern slavery and human rights statements, codes of conduct and governance arrangements from seven UK and five German supermarkets with qualitative fieldwork with key actors. Its objectives are to map the design and implementation of these frameworks in both chains, analyse their interaction with commercial strategies and purchasing practices, assess their effects on working conditions and the vulnerability of migrant and seasonal workers, and identify good practices and structural bottlenecks with implications for regulation and business practice. The remainder of the report sets out the methodology, develops the conceptual framework, presents the two case studies, offers a structured comparison of risks and governance and concludes with a synthesis of findings and recommendations.

1. Methodology and research design

The research analyses how supermarkets CSR and HRDD frameworks influence working conditions and OHS in strawberry value chains oriented towards export. It focuses on two comparative cases: the Huelva-Germany strawberry chain and the Morocco-United Kingdom strawberry chain.

The research design combines documentary analysis and qualitative fieldwork carried out within the project. The Grant Agreement envisaged semi structured interviews, including interviews with director level profiles, and a review of existing documentation on the design and implementation of CSR practices in five supermarkets, one German and four UK based. The final implementation maintained the semi structured interview approach, but in one case, instead of conducting an individual semi structured interview, a focus group was held within the UK chain with people in positions of responsibility, mainly Human Rights and Sustainability directors. This decision followed the supermarkets' own recommendation that

a peer discussion format would yield richer and more contrasted information than a single one to one interview.

In parallel, the documentary analysis was expanded to 12 supermarkets, five German and seven UK based, reviewing corporate reports, strategies and action plans. This additional work was carried out deliberately to provide greater quality, depth and detail to the report, without changing the core objectives of the research.

The focus group session lasted 90 minutes and was moderated by the author of the report, using the same thematic guide that had been used for the interview with the German supermarket, adapted to a group format. The guide covered Human Rights and Sustainability policies and strategies, supply chain management, supplier engagement and the main challenges identified. The focus group material was analysed in an integrated way together with the interviews, using the same thematic framework for qualitative analysis, so that its contributions complement and nuance the findings from the individual interviews and help strengthen the robustness and level of detail of the report.

Research objectives and questions

The overall objective is to assess how CSR and HRDD frameworks are designed and implemented in supermarket led strawberry value chains and how these frameworks affect working conditions and OHS for workers in exporting regions.

The report addresses, in a summarised form, four questions:

1. How German and UK supermarkets define their CSR and HRDD responsibilities, and which governance, risk management and grievance mechanisms they put in place to ensure compliance with human rights due diligence.
2. How the CSR and HRDD frameworks, along with the binding regulations, are translated into concrete practices in the Huelva-Germany and Morocco-United Kingdom chains in areas such as audits, purchasing practices, labour formalisation and OHS.
3. How agents, suppliers or importers and producers perceive the effects of these practices on wages, working time, housing, OHS and the capacity of workers to exercise their rights.
4. Which similarities and differences exist between the two chains in terms of residual social risks, structural drivers of vulnerability and the distribution of power and value; and which implications follow for regulation and the future implementation of HRDD.

Methodological approach

A mixed methods approach has been adopted, based on a comparative case study design. On one hand, documentary analysis of corporate policies, human rights and modern slavery statements, codes of conduct and due diligence reports allow for a reconstruction of how supermarkets formulate their responsibilities and report on their actions. On the other hand, semi structured interviews and the focus group provide evidence on how these frameworks are interpreted and experienced on farms and in the intermediary segments of the chains.

The comparison between the Huelva-Germany and Morocco-United Kingdom chains, located in different regulatory environments, makes it possible to analyse how distinct legal and governance frameworks shape the design and effectiveness of CSR and HRDD instruments, identifying both chain specific dynamics and more general patterns.

Case study selection

The selection of the two chains is purposive and responds to three main criteria:

1. Relevance in the European soft fruit market, given the weight of both chains in supplying major supermarkets.
2. Regulatory differences between a context with binding supply chain due diligence legislation in Germany and a context based on transparency and voluntary frameworks in the UK.
3. Documented labour and social risks in Huelva and in Moroccan producing regions, especially concerning migrant and seasonal workers.

Data collection

Document analysis

The documentary corpus includes:

- Corporate human rights and modern slavery statements, CSR or sustainability reports and supply chain due diligence reports.
- Supplier codes of conduct, ethical trading policies and guidance documents addressing audits, responsible recruitment and grievance mechanisms.
- Human rights impact assessments, where available, with particular attention to the Huelva-Germany chain.

- Reports by NGOs, research centres and public institutions on migrant agricultural work, supermarket governance of value chains and HRDD implementation in agriculture.

In total, corporate documentation from seven supermarkets in the UK and five in Germany were analysed. These supermarkets were selected because of their central role in the studied value chains. Documents were collected via corporate websites and transparency registers and analysed using a codebook consistent with the analytical framework set out in section 2.6. The documentary analysis covers materials published and/or accessible up to November 2025.

Interviews and focus group

A total of 15 semi structured interviews and one focus group were conducted:

Table 1: Interviews and focus groups conducted as part of the research

Chain	Method	Participant type	Number of participants
Huelva - Germany	Interviews	Independent experts (agents) with in depth knowledge of the berries sector	2
Huelva - Germany	Interviews	Strawberry producing companies based in Huelva	3
Huelva - Germany	Interviews	Suppliers or importing firms that connect Huelva producers with German supermarkets	2
Huelva - Germany	Interviews	Supermarket representative from a German supermarket	1
Morocco - United Kingdom	Interviews	Independent experts (agents) on the Moroccan	2

		strawberry value chain	
Morocco - United Kingdom	Interviews	Strawberry producing companies in Morocco	4
Morocco - United Kingdom	Interviews	Suppliers that connect these producers to UK supermarkets	2
Morocco - United Kingdom	Focus group	Supermarket representatives from UK	5

The interviews and the focus group addressed topics such as the evolution of supermarket requirements, experience with audits and certifications, purchasing practices and their impact on planning and risk distribution, recruitment and labour formalisation practices, working time and wages, housing and transport, and the functioning and perceived effectiveness of grievance and remediation mechanisms. The interviews and focus group were conducted during 2025. Interviews were conducted both in person and online. In-person interviews took place in Huelva and in the Gharb-Loukkos region in north-western Morocco, between the cities of Larache and Rabat along the Atlantic coast, while the focus group was held online. Interviews were conducted in Spanish and Arabic, depending on participant preference. In some cases, participants requested that the interview should not be recorded, but they authorised detailed note taking.

Sample and sampling strategy

The sample was constructed through purposive sampling, targeting actors with a deep knowledge of the chains and direct experience of their social and labour dynamics, complemented by snowball sampling. Diversity was sought in:

- Position in the chain (expert agents, producers, cooperatives and export companies, suppliers).
- Farm size, including both medium and large operations and smaller producers.
- Contexts where the vulnerability of migrant and seasonal workers, documented in previous research, is especially relevant for understanding residual risks.

Participation was voluntary and unpaid. All interviewees requested anonymity; therefore the identities of individuals, companies and farms are kept confidential and only aggregated or anonymised information is presented.

Analytical framework

The analysis is grounded in an integrated framework combining three bodies of literature and practice:

1. CSR and HRDD, to understand how supermarkets define responsibilities, design risk management systems and move from voluntary approaches towards more demanding due diligence models.
2. Global value chain (GVC) and food systems research, which situates HRDD within broader power relations, standard setting and the distribution of risks and margins in supermarket led chains.
3. Frameworks on the vulnerability of migrant and mobile workers, which highlight the role of legal status, recruitment channels, employer linked housing and transport, and gendered and racialised dynamics.

Interviews and documents were thematically coded according to this framework and HRDD risk categories. Based on this coding, a comparative matrix was developed covering several key dimensions and classifying residual risks in each chain as low, medium or high, thus identifying structural bottlenecks and chain specific patterns.

Qualitative information was analysed using a thematic analysis approach. In practice, the analysis was carried out in Excel using a structured matrix. A codebook was developed based on the analytical framework and the interview and focus group guides, including categories and subcategories with operational definitions (and was iteratively refined as new themes emerged). Final themes and subthemes were derived by combining a deductive approach (grounded in the framework and research questions) with an inductive approach (based on recurring patterns in the material), consolidating and refining categories through successive review rounds. As coding was conducted by a single researcher, no intercoder reliability metrics were applied; however, analytical coherence was strengthened through internal review and triangulation, as described in Section 2.7.

Quality assurance measures

Two main types of measures were applied to strengthen the robustness of the findings:

- Source triangulation: corporate documents, interview material and secondary literature were systematically compared, seeking to corroborate relevant statements using more than one type of source or stakeholder group.

- Internal peer review: interim findings were read by external experts in the field, who helped to question assumptions, refine interpretations and reduce individual bias.

Ethical considerations

The research adheres to ethical standards for studies on labour rights and corporate practices in high-risk contexts. Participants were informed about the objectives of the study, the voluntary nature of their participation, the intended use of the data, and their right not to answer specific questions or to withdraw at any time without consequences. All participants requested that their involvement remain anonymous. In some cases, they did not consent to audio recording but did authorise detailed note taking. Reporting preserves the anonymity of individuals and companies and avoids the identification of specific farms, while still allowing structural patterns and relevant illustrative examples to be presented.

Regarding ethical oversight, this study did not require formal ethics committee approval, as Oxfam Intermón does not operate under an institutional research ethics committee for this type of applied research. Nevertheless, the research was designed and implemented in line with Oxfam Intermón's Code of Conduct and the ethical principles that guide all Oxfam Intermón interventions, including a strong duty of care, the minimisation of risks for participants and an emphasis on confidentiality and responsible data handling.

Data protection and privacy were addressed throughout the research process. Personal data, recordings and notes were kept under the exclusive custody of the research team and were not accessible to third parties. All research materials were stored in secure internal team storage folders with access restricted exclusively to authorised members of the research team. Access controls were used to limit visibility and prevent unauthorised sharing. In line with GDPR principles, the research applied data minimisation (collecting only what was necessary), purpose limitation (using data only for the stated research objectives), and confidentiality safeguards. Any personal identifiers were removed or pseudonymised as early as possible, and only anonymised information was used for analysis and reporting.

With respect to retention, data was kept only for as long as necessary to complete the analysis, quality assurance and reporting requirements of the project, and will be securely deleted once no longer required for these purposes, in line with the team's internal data management practices.

Finally, the team applied a precautionary approach to sensitive disclosures, including any potential references to labour rights violations. Interviews and the focus group were conducted in a way that avoided prompting participants to disclose unnecessary personal or identifying details. Where sensitive information emerged, it was handled with strict confidentiality, recorded in anonymised form, and reported only at an aggregated level to reduce any risk of harm or retaliation. Where relevant, the research team prioritised

participant safety and ensured that no information was included in the report that could reasonably lead to the identification of individuals, companies or specific farms.

2. Conceptual-Contextual Framework: CSR, Due Diligence, etc.

Theoretical foundations of CSR in agricultural value chains

CSR in supermarket-led agrifood chains: concepts and governance approaches

CSR is commonly understood as a company's voluntary integration of social and ethical concerns into business operations and stakeholder relations, going "beyond" strict legal compliance. In the European food sector, this framing has frequently been expressed as a call for companies to internalize social responsibilities across supply chains, not merely within their own facilities (Benito Hernández, 2019, pp. 4-5). In supermarket-led agrifood chains, CSR therefore denotes the policies, codes, and programs through which supermarkets and their suppliers purport to address labour rights, health and safety, environmental protection, and decent work across production networks that extend from farms and packhouses to logistics and distribution.

A useful map of CSR in agribusiness identifies four approaches: (a) GVC; (b) environmental issues; (c) regulation and international private standards; and (d) strategy (Lizcano Prada & Lombana, 2018, p. 349). For our social-focused analysis, two are particularly salient. First, GVC perspectives emphasize how buyer governance shapes upstream practices. Supermarkets' commercial strategies, especially in fresh produce, confer substantial coordination power over dispersed growers; fresh fruit and vegetables are used to attract and retain consumers, incentivizing stringent control over suppliers' processes (Lizcano Prada & Lombana, 2018, p. 352). In such "buyer-driven" chains, CSR instruments (codes, audits, capacity building) operate as mechanisms of private governance that diffuse social norms and allocate responsibilities along tiers.

Second, a strand focused on private standards and regulation examines the proliferation of private standards and certification in a context of limited public regulation regarding social performance in global agriculture. Here, CSR merges with private rule setting and market access, where supermarkets require suppliers to demonstrate conformity with social codes as a condition of trade (Lizcano Prada & Lombana, 2018, pp. 353-354). This literature recognizes both benefits, such as greater visibility of social issues and diffusion of norms,

and governance limits, such as weak accountability to workers and the limited voice of small producers in standard-setting processes (Lizcano Prada & Lombana, 2018, p. 354).

Stakeholder- and strategy-oriented lenses complement these governance approaches. Stakeholder accounts argue that agrifood CSR must respond to the claims of multiple actors (workers, smallholders, consumers, communities) and be embedded in collaborative arrangements rather than unilateral auditing (Lizcano Prada & Lombana, 2018, p. 352). Strategic perspectives, in turn, emphasize CSR as a risk management and differentiation tool within competitive retail markets. At the same time, these studies caution that CSR alone does not resolve the underlying tensions between commercial imperatives and social objectives and must be situated within broader organisational and governance change (Lizcano Prada & Lora Monsalve, 2024, pp. 176-177).

From CSR to business and human rights: human rights due diligence and key critiques

Across these approaches, agricultural CSR increasingly references business and human rights (BHR) principles, in particular HRDD, to structure the identification and mitigation of risks to people rather than risks to companies. The UN Guiding Principles (UNGPs) conceptualize HRDD as an ongoing, risk-based process of identifying, preventing, mitigating and accounting for adverse human rights impacts (Bonnitcha & McCorquodale, 2017, p. 902). In supermarket-driven strawberry chains, this frames CSR not as philanthropy but as the systematic management of human rights risks across supply chains, including, among other things, labour-related risks such as forced labour, excessive working hours, or hazardous tasks in harvesting and packing, as well as broader issues such as land tenure impacts and the distribution of value affecting farmers' livelihoods.

At the same time, three critiques recur in the food sector literature and inform how BHR is taken up in practice. First, voluntary standards may substitute for, rather than complement, robust public enforcement and worker voice; standard-setting power concentrates with buyers, while small producers and workers have limited say (Lizcano Prada & Lombana, 2018, p. 354). Second, CSR programs can remain primarily supply-push, focused on supplier compliance, rather than demand-pull, driven by changes in supermarket purchasing practices. As a result, price and lead-time pressures, which are key determinants of working conditions, often remain unchanged. Third, CSR frequently stays process-oriented (emphasizing the existence of policies, audits, and reports) rather than outcome-oriented (emphasizing accountability to affected people and measurable improvements), a gap that BHR frameworks explicitly seek to narrow (Albarracín Bohorquez & Lora Monsalve, 2024, pp. 176-177).

These debates shape how we later interpret interview material from Spanish-German and Moroccan-United Kingdom chains. CSR instruments, whether framed in conventional CSR

language or under BHR and HRDD, must be read against the broader governance context and purchasing practices that condition their effectiveness in improving labour standards.

Due diligence frameworks and legal requirements

Human rights due diligence under the UNGPs: from soft to hard law

The UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights define HRDD as a standard of conduct requiring companies to put in place processes to identify, prevent, mitigate, and account for how they address adverse human rights impacts linked to their operations, products, or services, including through their business relationships (Bonnitcha & McCorquodale, 2017, p. 902). Crucially, “due diligence” in this framework refers to what is reasonable in the circumstances, an effort standard rather than a guarantee of particular outcomes, yet it is explicitly person-centred: the benchmark is the severity and likelihood of harm to rights holders, rather than risk to the enterprise (Bonnitcha & McCorquodale, 2017, pp. 900-902). In agricultural value chains, this distinction is particularly significant, as risks to seasonal and migrant workers, such as recruitment fees, unsafe or overcrowded housing, or exposure to extreme heat, must be prioritised because of their severity and potential irremediability.

The UNGPs themselves are “soft law”: they are authoritative but not legally binding. Nonetheless, they have catalysed a wider regulatory shift by providing the conceptual template for binding (“hard law”) HRDD regimes. Soft-law instruments such as transparency statements and voluntary codes can raise awareness and promote norm diffusion, but they typically lack enforceable duties, robust supervision, or meaningful sanctions. A paradigmatic example is the UK MSA, whose Section 54 requires certain businesses to publish an annual modern slavery statement but does not prescribe specific HRDD steps, nor does it create civil liability for failing to undertake due diligence (Bonnitcha & McCorquodale, 2017, pp. 907-908). In contrast, emerging HREDD statutes in Europe, such as the German LkSG and the EU CSDDD, impose explicit obligations, public oversight, and penalties, and thereby move agricultural CSR from voluntary, process-oriented commitments towards more outcome-oriented accountability.

German Supply Chain Due Diligence Act (LkSG) and the Huelva-Germany chain

The German Supply Chain Due Diligence Act (Lieferkettensorgfaltspflichtengesetz, LkSG), which entered into force in 2023, obliges in-scope companies to establish a comprehensive risk-management system, carry out regular human rights and environmental risk analyses, issue a policy statement, implement preventive and remedial measures, set up an accessible complaints procedure, address certain risks at indirect suppliers, and document and report on these efforts (Supply Chain Due Diligence Act, 2021). The Act initially applied to companies

with at least 3,000 employees in Germany (from January 2023) and, from 2024, extends to those with at least 1,000 employees in Germany, covering both private and publicly owned undertakings. It encompasses human rights, labour, and health-and-safety risks across a company's own operations and its supply chain, including direct suppliers and, under defined circumstances, indirect suppliers.

For German supermarkets sourcing strawberries from Huelva, Spain, the LkSG formally requires risk analysis of field-level and packhouse-level risks, such as complex subcontracting chains, employer-provided accommodation, etc., followed by appropriate preventive and remedial measures and the establishment of effective grievance channels at supplier sites (Supply Chain Due Diligence Act, 2021). Sector-specific analyses underline that agriculture presents distinctive HRDD challenges because of fragmented production structures, high seasonality, and heavy reliance on intermediaries; effective implementation thus typically requires engagement beyond first-tier suppliers and adaptation to heterogeneous farm sizes and organisational forms (Rudloff, Wieck, Iweala, & Spiller, 2025, pp. 1-3, 13).

UK Modern Slavery Act (MSA) and the Morocco-UK chain

The UK Modern Slavery Act 2015 adopts a transparency-based model rather than a fully-fledged HRDD regime (Modern Slavery Act, 2015). Section 54 ("Transparency in supply chains") requires large commercial organisations supplying goods or services in the UK and meeting a specified turnover threshold to prepare and publish an annual slavery and human trafficking statement, approved at board level and signed by a director. The provision lists areas that companies may report on, such as policies, due diligence processes, and risk assessment, but does not mandate particular HRDD steps, nor does it create civil liability or explicit financial penalties for failing to undertake due diligence; enforcement relies largely on reputational pressure and the possibility of injunctive relief. Empirical assessments suggest substantial unevenness in the quality and completeness of corporate statements, pointing to the structural limits of a transparency only model.

In the Morocco-United Kingdom strawberry chain, UK supermarkets are therefore primarily subject to a reporting duty. The MSA can incentivise programmes such as third-party audits, supplier training on modern slavery risks, and worker hotlines, so far as supermarkets wish to demonstrate progress in their public statements. Yet in the absence of binding HRDD obligations specifying minimum risk-management steps and sanctions for non-compliance, there remains a structural risk of uneven depth, coverage, and continuity of such measures across suppliers, seasons, and labour contractors.

EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD)

The EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD, Directive 2024/1760) established a harmonised framework of human rights and environmental due diligence (HREDD) for large EU and non-EU companies operating in the internal market. Companies in scope must integrate due diligence into their policies and risk management systems; identify, assess, prevent, mitigate, bring to an end, and remediate adverse human rights and environmental impacts arising from their own operations, those of their subsidiaries, or of business partners in their supply chains; engage with stakeholders; and provide access to remediation. The Directive also requires Member States to foresee supervisory authorities and administrative sanctions (e.g. fines) for non-compliance, and it specifies the measures companies are expected to take to prevent and mitigate adverse impacts, including seeking contractual assurances from direct business partners and making changes to business plans and operations, including purchasing practices (Articles 10 and 11).

When it first came into force in July 2024, the CSDDD provided a EU-wide harmonized civil liability regime, but following the changes imposed by the “Omnibus I” package, this was removed, leaving civil liability rules up to Member State law (Council of the European Union, 2025).

Originally, the CSDDD would have been applied in phases according to employee and turnover thresholds, beginning with very large companies (over 5,000 employees and EUR 1.5 billion global net turnover), been progressively extended to companies with more than 3,000 employees and EUR 900 million, and eventually applied to companies with more than 1,000 employees and EUR 450 million, alongside equivalent thresholds for non-EU companies with significant EU-generated turnover (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2024; 2025). Following the “Omnibus I” package, the entire scope of the CSDDD has been limited to the first section of very large companies (over 5,000 employees and EUR 1.5 billion global net turnover), the transposition deadline has been postponed from 26 July 2026 to 26 July 2028, and the application to in-scope companies has been delayed by two years, from July 2027 to July 2029 (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2025).

For supermarkets operating in EU markets, the CSDDD is expected to standardise expectations around supplier risk assessment, worker engagement, and remediation in both the Spain-Germany and Morocco-United Kingdom strawberry chains (the latter through the Directive’s extraterritorial coverage of value chains when EU-based entities are involved). Agricultural analyses emphasise the importance of aligning CSDDD implementation with existing sectoral schemes and certifications, avoiding regulatory fragmentation, and ensuring proportionality for smallholders and other vulnerable upstream actors (Rudloff et al., 2025, pp. 12-13).

From voluntarism to enforceable duties in supermarket-led strawberry chains

Compared with traditional CSR voluntarism, binding HRDD regimes such as the LkSG and the CSDDD require supermarkets not merely to “have a code” but to demonstrate: (i) systematic risk analysis focused on the severity of impacts on people; (ii) documented preventive and remedial measures tailored to identified risks; (iii) accessible, trusted grievance mechanisms; and (iv) public reporting subject to regulatory oversight and potential sanctions (Bonnitcha & McCorquodale, 2017, pp. 902, 917-919; Supply Chain Due Diligence Act, 2021; European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2024).

In supermarket-driven strawberry chains, this implies a shift from a narrow focus on supplier audits and certification to end-to-end risk governance encompassing recruitment channels, labour providers, accommodation and transport arrangements, and subcontracting relationships, areas that empirical research repeatedly identifies as loci of abuse in agricultural labour markets. Rather than treating HRDD as a reporting exercise, enforceable duties require supermarkets and their lead suppliers to engage with workers and local stakeholders, address structural drivers such as purchasing practices and price pressures, and ensure that remediation is available and accessible to affected workers in both the Huelva-Germany and Morocco-United Kingdom chains.

Power dynamics in global food systems

Conceptualising and locating power in supermarket-led food systems

Power in food systems operates across multiple dimensions. At an economic and organisational level, it includes bargaining power (who sets prices, quantities, and lead times), informational power (control over data, traceability, and performance metrics), standard-setting power (the ability to impose private codes and requirements), and symbolic power (the capacity to shape framing, narratives, and legitimacy claims). Analyses of twenty-first-century food systems underline the concentration of market and political power in large food companies and supermarkets, and how market dominance is translated into influence over public policy and governance arrangements (Swinburn, 2019, pp. 2, 5-8).

UNDP’s (United Nations Development Programme) scoping work on “food and power” complements these dimensions with a fourfold typology: visible power (formal rules, institutions, and policies), hidden power (control over agendas by corporate and financial actors), invisible power (norms, narratives, and internalised assumptions), and systemic power (deeply embedded structures such as global trade regimes or financial architectures) (UNDP, 2025, p. 2). Taken together, these perspectives highlight that power in food systems is not only about observable decisions (e.g. price setting) but also about who defines the

terms of debate, which issues become visible, and how structural conditions constrain the range of possible actions.

In supermarket-driven, buyer-led agricultural chains, these power dimensions are distributed asymmetrically. Supermarkets wield bargaining and standard-setting power through contracting terms, last-minute orders, and private compliance requirements. First-tier suppliers (exporters, packers) translate these demands into upstream specifications and performance pressures, while growers, especially smaller farms, absorb a large share of commercial risk (price volatility, quality standards, timing) and transmit variability to workers through hiring practices, piece rates, and working hours.

GVC research shows that supermarkets' governance of fresh produce is central to their competitive strategy, reinforcing their capacity to discipline suppliers and shape production practices (Lizcano Prada & Lombana, 2018, p. 352). UNDP further emphasises that corporate concentration in the retail sector can "squeeze" producers' margins and influence broader policy environments, consolidating both visible and hidden forms of power (UNDP, 2025, pp. 2-3).

Power, accountability, and the CSR-HRDD shift

Swinburn argues that declarations of "responsibility" by powerful food system actors need to be translated into accountability, enforceable expectations backed by oversight, and consequences (2019, p. 8). This reframing parallels the transition from voluntary CSR to mandatory HRDD. Under this shift, visible power in governance moves, at least partially, from unilateral private codes and standards towards public law duties (for example under the German Supply Chain Due Diligence Act, LkSG, and the forthcoming EU CSDDD). This creates the potential to redistribute some of the costs and responsibilities of compliance away from growers alone towards supermarkets and first-tier suppliers who design purchasing and sourcing practices.

However, the persistence of hidden and invisible power limits how far this shift can go. Purchasing norms such as short lead times, unpredictable orders, or strict just in time logistics can undermine social commitments if they are not aligned with HRDD-based risk mitigation. Even where legal obligations exist, supermarkets may retain informational power (through control of audit data and supplier ratings) and symbolic power (through narratives of "sustainable sourcing"), which can shape the interpretation and implementation of HRDD in ways that leave underlying commercial pressures largely intact.

Migrant and mobile worker vulnerability frameworks

Structural drivers of migrant and mobile worker vulnerability

Conceptual frameworks on agricultural labour vulnerability underline how legal status, recruitment channels, housing dependence on employers, language barriers, racialisation, gendered divisions of labour, seasonality, and the role of intermediaries interact to shape risk exposure and constrain workers' agency. A recent synthesis for Europe documents how migrant workers are recruited both in destination countries and at origin (including via posting arrangements), often incurring fees or deductions; how many workers reside in employer-provided or otherwise inadequate housing; and how piecework, fluctuating hours, and subcontracting are routine features of agricultural employment (Ruiz Ramírez et al., 2024, pp. 5-6, 10-12, 18-21, 23-25).

Legal and administrative status. Short-term seasonal permits and irregular status reduce workers' bargaining power and their ability to seek remedy. Even exploitative contracts may be perceived as a potential route to regularisation, thereby increasing dependence on employers (Ruiz Ramírez et al., 2024, p. 6). In the Spanish context, this intersects with seasonal recruitment regimes; in Morocco-Europe circuits, origin-based recruitment can align gender and migration controls with labour demand, shaping vulnerability profiles without necessarily providing effective protection (a framing drawn from the synthesis rather than from case-specific anecdotes) (Ruiz Ramírez et al., 2024, pp. 5-6).

Recruitment and intermediaries. Labour intermediation, whether via licensed agencies, brokers, or informal arrangements, can externalise employer risks and fragment accountability. Deductions for transport, accommodation, or "services" erode net wages and obscure who is responsible for abusive practices (Ruiz Ramírez et al., 2024, pp. 19-21). These dynamics are particularly salient in horticulture, where short harvest windows create demand spikes that intermediaries are called upon to fill.

Housing and transport dependence. Employer-provided or remote housing can intensify isolation, restrict access to services, and create de facto captive labour markets. Overcrowded and substandard living conditions are widely reported, as are mobility barriers due to inadequate or employer-controlled transport (Ruiz Ramírez et al., 2024, pp. 22-25).

Language, racialisation, and gender. Language barriers hinder understanding of rights, contractual terms, and safety procedures. Racialised stereotypes and discrimination reinforce unequal treatment and differential access to better jobs or protections. Women workers face gender-specific risks, including constrained mobility, unequal distribution of care responsibilities, and exposure to harassment and gender-based violence (Ruiz Ramírez et al., 2024, pp. 28-29).

Seasonality and piecework. Seasonal peaks interact with piece-rate systems to encourage self-exploitation, workers driving themselves to work faster or longer to reach quotas, and to normalise excessive hours or unpaid waiting time, with significant OHS implications (Ruiz Ramírez et al., 2024, pp. 18-19, 31-35).

Taken together, these dimensions show that migrant and mobile worker vulnerability is produced through the intersection of legal regimes, labour market structures, and social hierarchies, rather than being an incidental or purely individual condition.

3. Case study: Huelva (Spain) - Germany value chain

Analysis of human rights, CSR and due diligence policies of selected supermarkets

Overview

This section analyses corporate documents from five German supermarkets involved in the Huelva-Germany strawberry supply chain that set out their human rights, CSR, and HRDD policies. The analysis consolidates human rights and modern slavery statements, supplier codes of conduct, ethical trading policies, governance arrangements and HRDD practices, and reads these sources with specific reference to their relevance for strawberry sourcing from Huelva for the German market. In addition to the documentary analysis, insights from an interview with a German supermarket operating in the Huelva berry supply chain are incorporated, in order to nuance and contrast the due diligence architecture described in public documents.

Across the sampled supermarkets, public commitments consistently affirm respect for internationally recognised human rights and labour standards throughout corporate operations and agricultural supply chains. Policies are anchored in global norms and require suppliers to prohibit forced and child labour, uphold non-discrimination, ensure safe and decent working conditions, and respect freedom of association and collective bargaining. Several supermarkets explicitly align their approaches with international frameworks such as the International Bill of Human Rights, the core conventions of the International Labour Organization (ILO) and the UNGPs on Business and Human Rights, and in some cases refer to the OECD (The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises. These standards are framed as binding expectations for all business partners and apply across agricultural supply chains. Explicit references to the

Huelva-Germany strawberry route are not always present in overarching policy declarations, but the commitments are formulated as enterprise wide and therefore cover this chain.

Governance structures place accountability at senior levels. Human rights and due diligence statements are approved by boards or top management, with day-to-day implementation overseen by designated human rights, sustainability or corporate responsibility functions. Some supermarkets describe cross functional coordination between procurement, sustainability, legal and compliance teams to integrate human rights considerations into business risk management and sourcing decisions. In addition, where national supply chain due diligence legislation applies, companies state that they have adapted internal governance and reporting processes to meet those requirements.

The interviewed supermarket emphasises that this evolution is not limited to adopting strategic documents, but has also involved greater organisational specialisation, with a clear division of tasks between risk analysis, monitoring and reporting, aimed at making human rights commitments more systematic and measurable.

Risk Identification and Prioritisation

Supermarkets describe structured risk identification that combines periodic (often annual) analyses with event-driven reassessments. Screening typically considers country context, commodity sector, workforce profile, and tier complexity. Tools cited include third-party platforms for supplier risk mapping and internal scoring matrices; suppliers in higher-risk categories are flagged for deeper scrutiny via questionnaires, targeted information requests, and follow-up engagement. Salient risks prioritized across agricultural supply chains include forced labour, child labour, excessive working hours, wage underpayment, unsafe conditions, and discrimination, with explicit attention to the higher vulnerability of seasonal and migrant workers. While Huelva is not named in standard risk maps, supermarkets identify fruit and vegetable chains in Southern Europe as requiring enhanced vigilance, implying relevance to the Huelva-Germany context.

The evidence base also includes an impact assessment carried out by one supermarket that focuses on the Huelva-Germany strawberry chain as a case of strategic importance, noting the concentration of seasonal labour and the need for a granular understanding of gender and migration dynamics. This deeper analysis supplements the general risk framework with chain-specific findings (see “Regional and Sectoral Focus” below).

According to the interviewed supermarket, the Huelva berry chain is internally classified as a high-risk segment within the wider group of agricultural suppliers, which translates into systematic annual reviews and heightened attention to risks such as housing conditions, gender dynamics, recruitment channels and reliance on temporary and migrant labour.

These assessments are used to decide where to concentrate preventive measures and remediation interventions.

Implementation and Operational Measures

Implementation measures span supplier standards, auditing, training, recruitment protocols, and collaborative initiatives. Social compliance audits (e.g., widely used third party audit formats) are required for higher risk sites; audits examine documentation, conduct worker interviews, and assess health and safety. Corrective action planning is standard where non-conformities are found, and progress is tracked in subsequent reviews. Whether audits are announced or unannounced is not consistently specified in public materials, although in some higher risk chains supermarkets refer to random unannounced social audits.

Evidence from the interview with a German supermarket indicates that since 2019 all direct suppliers in the Huelva berry chain must hold a GLOBALG.A.P. Risk Assessment on Social Practice (GRASP) certificate or equivalent for risk-oriented verification of minimum social standards. Recent assessments reportedly show that hundreds of producers fully meet these requirements, and the interview notes that these schemes are complemented by additional social audits that may be carried out unannounced and focus on previously identified areas of concern.

Responsible recruitment is emphasized through the “employer pays” principle and requirements to use licensed labour providers with written contracts; undisclosed subcontracting is prohibited. Supplier training is described for both internal staff (e.g., buyer awareness of human rights obligations) and external partners, with targeted e learning or workshops aligned to risk findings. The standards are explicit that protections apply equally to temporary, seasonal, and migrant workers, including the requirement that terms be communicated in a language they understand and that employer provided housing and transport meet baseline conditions.

The interviewed supermarket reports a specific action plan for the Huelva berry chain that includes strengthening internal due diligence capacity, expanding monitoring of cooperatives and producer companies, requiring key supply chain agents to comply with sustainable purchasing policies, participation in sector initiatives such as the Spanish Ethical Trade Forum and Stronger Together, targeted training on the prevention of forced labour with specialised organisations, and the joint development with suppliers of clearer measures on housing and transport.

In the Huelva strawberry chain, supermarkets complement baseline schemes (such as farm level social control modules used in agriculture) with closer oversight, continuous improvement plans, and, in some instances, additional, more specialized social audits at

higher risk entities. Action plans include strengthening worker voice mechanisms and supporting freedom of association at producer level.

Monitoring, Traceability, and Transparency

Traceability efforts involve mapping sub-tiers to the farm level for high-risk commodities, supported by supplier data platforms. Some supermarkets indicate an ambition to publish supplier information for selected categories; in at least one case, suppliers in the strawberry chain are already disclosed down to farm level, while others provide less detailed public information. Internally, companies monitor indicators such as audit coverage, non-compliance closure rates, training volumes, and grievance channel usage. While some quantitative indicators are reported at aggregate level, detailed labour-related key performance indicators (KPIs) disaggregated by supply chain, including specific data on working time, wages, and housing conditions in Huelva, are generally not available in public documents. However, corporate narratives emphasize continuous review and the integration of monitoring results into procurement decisions. Public reporting through annual human rights or due diligence statements is standard, with alignment across codes, due diligence reports, and corporate responsibility policies.

In chain-specific work on Huelva, supermarkets describe mapping of actors (from producers and cooperatives to export agents), routine review of social assessment results, and feedback loops to adjust standards, audit frequency, and buyer practices. Group-wide policies are stated to apply across all private-label supply chains and subsidiaries, with commitments to publish periodic updates under applicable due diligence reporting regimes.

The interviewed supermarket adds that supplier risk analyses are updated at least once a year, using criteria such as severity and likelihood of harm, leverage and contribution to risk, and that the results are used both to identify high risk supply chains that require additional measures and to track progress on Huelva specific action plans in annual human rights progress reports.

Grievance and Remedy Mechanisms

Supermarkets maintain multi-channel grievance systems accessible to internal staff and external stakeholders, including workers in supply chains. These channels are typically confidential, available in multiple languages, and include third-party hotlines or web portals; non-retaliation commitments are specified. Companies also participate in, or support, independent or multi-stakeholder mechanisms relevant to agricultural contexts. Public materials describe procedures for logging, assessing, and investigating complaints; where harm is caused or contributed to, remedial action is pursued through corrective plans, with escalation to suspension or termination where remediation fails. Data on volume and typology of supply-chain grievances is limited, though several supermarkets commit to

evaluate mechanism effectiveness against recognized criteria and to report on improvements over time.

The information from the interview points to a gradual expansion of these systems in the Huelva berry supply chain, including an online complaints platform available in numerous languages and accessible across global supply chains, as well as the establishment of a local grievance mechanism in Huelva that has contributed to the design of a new inter-retailer mechanism in the Spanish fruit and vegetable sector, intended to allow workers at producer level to report social and environmental concerns without fear of discrimination

Chain-specific measures for Huelva include plans to reinforce access to trusted channels for seasonal and migrant workers, strengthen local partnerships to handle complaints, and ensure that learning from cases informs both supplier requirements and internal buying practices.

Regional and Sectoral Focus: Huelva-Germany Strawberry Supply Chain

Although the general human rights and CSR policy texts do not refer to Huelva explicitly, a dedicated human rights impact assessment focuses specifically on the Huelva-Germany strawberry supply chain and identifies structural risks linked to the intensity of seasonal labour, gendered vulnerabilities and inadequate worker housing conditions. The resulting action plan provides for enhanced social monitoring in this chain, the strengthening of worker voice and freedom of association, measures to reduce last-minute ordering pressures, and greater cost and pricing transparency aimed at ensuring that legal wage costs are consistently covered. In addition, supermarkets commit to supporting worker-facing grievances and information channels, including locally accessible mechanisms, to facilitate access to remedy for seasonal and migrant workers during the harvest period.

From the perspective of the interviewed supermarket, future priorities in this chain include making progress towards living wages and incomes in higher risk segments, consolidating effective and accessible grievance mechanisms for migrant and seasonal workers, and continuing to integrate the voice of workers, trade unions and civil society organisations in Huelva into risk identification and periodic review of the measures applied.

Impacts on the labour conditions of farm workers - Stakeholder Perspectives (agents, suppliers and growers)

Overview

This section analyses stakeholder perspectives on how supermarkets' CSR and HRDD frameworks, together with the structure of commercial relationships, influence working and

living conditions for seasonal labour in the strawberry value chain between Huelva and Germany. It draws on interviews with two independent experts, suppliers and importers, and growers, and examines their assessments of supermarkets' social requirements, audit and certification systems, expectations regarding compliance, and the functioning of grievance and remediation mechanisms. The analysis explores how these actors understand the role of German supermarkets in defining social standards, monitoring performance and distributing economic and social risks along the chain.

Agents

Independent agents underline that the relationship between intensive agriculture in Huelva and German supermarkets is structured around the purchasing power of German retail. Buyers effectively decide producers' survival in practice, imposing strict technical and cosmetic standards that split production into a "premium" category for Germany and a devalued remainder for secondary uses. This systematic downgrading of perfectly edible fruit squeezes profit margins and limits the scope to improve wages, stabilise contracts, or reduce work intensity.

They also stress that these quality requirements are tied to rigid logistics, with very tight delivery windows and last-minute orders that translate into longer working hours, frequent reorganisation of shifts, and extended working days, increasing pressure on workers even when the formal documentation appears to be in order. At the same time, they point out that the landscape of certifications and audits is dense and fragmented, and that the quality of social audits is highly uneven: they are often carried out by auditors with a technical agronomic profile and limited specific knowledge of labour relations, which favours reviews focused on paperwork and checklists rather than on detecting real problems. This combination of multiple standards and audits of variable quality multiplies controls and bureaucracy without ensuring equivalent improvements in working conditions, fostering a culture of "passing the audit" instead of addressing risks. According to these experts, the system does not reward producers who invest seriously in labour standards, since purchasing decisions remain dominated by price. They argue that meaningful change depends less on adding new labels and more on reforming how German supermarkets buy, so that compliant suppliers and less harmful logistical practices are genuinely valued.

Suppliers

In the opinion of suppliers, the berry supply chain oriented towards the German market is based on a very formalised social compliance regime whose quality is, however, doubtful: social audits are in most cases very poor, perceived as superficial, announced in advance and focused on checklists that generate documentation rather than a real understanding of working conditions. Added to this is a very high bureaucratic burden, including lengthy questionnaires, multiple platforms, traceability requirements and continuous demands for

evidence, which makes it particularly difficult for small and medium-sized producers to manage the requirements of the German market directly, placing significant strain on their administrative and economic capacity.

The interview describes how German buyers focus mainly on verifying, through audits and document review, that everything is in order, while showing little involvement in local projects or direct investments aimed at improving conditions in places of production. Their responsibility is exercised primarily through control, not through any kind of material co-responsibility: the origin is required to comply, but this compliance is rarely accompanied by resources or long-term commitments that would strengthen local capacities.

The technical and bureaucratic complexity of this system means that intermediary and exporting companies between Huelva and German supermarkets must assume a central role in translating and organising requirements so that farms can continue selling. This mediation partially alleviates the direct overload on producers, but it does not remove the underlying pressure. Instead, it concentrates it in a few structures that then transmit the demands down the chain, creating an increasingly costly and difficult compliance environment for those producing at origin.

The result is a model that encourages a certain formalisation of employment relations, such as more registered contracts, more social security enrolments, and basic human resources procedures, but in an ambivalent way. The logic of passing the audit and responding to bureaucratic expectations leads to superficial fixes and a defensive compliance culture that overstates improvement on paper compared to real changes in wages, working hours, job stability or collective organising capacity. The combination of low-quality audits, high documentary demands, a focus on control without local investment and a deeply asymmetric distribution of economic risk concentrates insecurity on producers and intermediaries, who pass it on into the organisation of work. Despite greater formalisation, the redistribution of power along the chain remains very limited, and improvements for workers at origin are partial, fragile and structurally weak.

Growers

Producers explain that in the Huelva-Germany value chain, effective control lies with large supermarkets who set the standards, specifications, prices, and have the power to accept or reject the fruit, while producers bear the burden of farm work, packaging, logistics, and paperwork. Their production planning is aligned with the commercial calendar of the German market and with competition from other producing countries, concentrating the campaign into just a few weeks and requiring investments in irrigation technology, cold storage, and work organization to ensure that a highly perishable fruit arrives in optimal condition after several days of transport to supermarket shelves.

Producers say that on top of this foundation, a web of social requirements is layered, structured through private certifications such as GLOBALG.A.P. and other labour and sustainability schemes, which function both as an entry toll to the German market and as a long-distance control mechanism. They point out that it is the supermarket that defines which certifications and auditing bodies are recognized, while the Huelva-based company must hire and pay for those audits and feed a system of documentation, surveys, and visits that must prove compliance with rules on wages, working hours, risk prevention, housing conditions, team organization, and rest periods. The relationship with German supermarkets thus involves not only shipping fruit but also maintaining a permanent file that certifies social correctness across all plots and farms.

They add that audits and visits by technicians and quality controllers, who inspect fields, warehouses, and accommodations, combining social and commercial monitoring, reinforce a very hierarchical governance system in which producers feel constantly evaluated but poorly protected from rejections and price deductions at the destination. They stress that this structure favours medium and large integrated companies that can sustain quality and sustainability departments, invest in dedicated housing for workers, and absorb the fixed costs of certification. In contrast, many small-scale farmers with few hectares are left either subordinate to cooperatives or excluded entirely from the circuits that supply German supermarkets directly, as they cannot handle that technical, administrative, and financial burden on their own.

From a commercial perspective, they explain that the combination of extreme perishability and rejection clauses that impose little or no cost on the buyer shifts the risk to the origin. When a truck is rejected in Germany, it is the producer who absorbs the cost of the fruit, the packaging, the transport, and potentially the destruction of the shipment, often with scarce information and response times that are incompatible with the short shelf life of strawberries.

In this context, the social requirements imposed by supermarkets are not seen in isolation but are interwoven with fruit quality standards and technical control systems. The need to harvest at a very precise point of ripeness to avoid rejections after two or three days of transport to Germany requires organizing the labour force with high availability during the campaign peak, implementing productivity tracking systems for each worker, and adjusting the pace of harvesting and handling. This creates tension between meeting social standards and maintaining the economic viability of the farm. They also note that they often face post hoc price adjustments justified by alleged quality issues or by market trends.

For all these reasons, they describe the Huelva-Germany relationship as a buyer-driven chain in which German supermarkets impose a formalized social and labour framework that

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producers must finance and implement while bearing the bulk of the economic risk associated with the strawberries consumed in the German market.

Comparative Matrix: Stakeholder Impacts on Farm Labour Conditions and OHS (Huelva-Germany)

Table 2: Comparative Matrix: Stakeholder Impacts on Farm Labour Conditions and OHS (Huelva-Germany)

Theme	Agents (independent experts - observer role)	Suppliers / Importers (intermediary companies)	Growers (farm owners / producer-exporters)
Labour Formalization (contracts, status)	Note that the standards architecture increases formalisation on paper but does not automatically secure sustained improvements in wages, working time or workers' bargaining power.	Audit requirements oblige companies to document contracts, payrolls, hours and grievance records, reducing informality but increasing administrative and compliance costs.	Farms supplying Germany keep detailed records of labour compliance; integrated operations can manage this, while smaller farms struggle with the administrative burden and often rely on intermediaries.
Purchasing Practices (pricing, orders)	Emphasise that low prices, strict cosmetic standards and just-in-time orders from Germany compress margins in Huelva and intensify labour on farms and especially in packing facilities.	Operate in a price-driven German market with rigid and sometimes opaque rejection practices, which shift substantial commercial risk back to origin and force cost pressures down the chain.	Adjust planting calendars, varieties and campaign length to German market windows and face highly asymmetric risk: a few rejections can erase the profits of multiple accepted shipments.

<p>Labour Formalization (contracts, status)</p>	<p>Note that the standards architecture increases formalisation on paper but does not automatically secure sustained improvements in wages, working time or workers' bargaining power.</p>	<p>Audit requirements oblige companies to document contracts, payrolls, hours and grievance records, reducing informality but increasing administrative and compliance costs.</p>	<p>Farms supplying Germany keep detailed records of labour compliance; integrated operations can manage this, while smaller farms struggle with the administrative burden and often rely on intermediaries.</p>
<p>Occupational Health & Safety (OHS)</p>	<p>Observe that commercial and logistical pressures towards Germany generate intense rhythms and unsocial hours, while environmental issues receive more attention than OHS in supermarket agendas.</p>	<p>Incorporate OHS into checklists and site visits (ergonomics, PPE, housing, transport), but the perishability of berries and risk of rejection drive high work intensity and limit real adjustments.</p>	<p>Implement OHS and housing requirements for certification, but peak-season labour demands and tight logistical windows create gaps between formal standards and everyday practice.</p>
<p>Reputational Dynamics (risk and response)</p>	<p>Highlight that CSR and due-diligence frameworks function mainly as tools for German supermarkets to manage reputational risk, with social requirements applied flexibly depending on market conditions.</p>	<p>Manage reputational expectations by providing documentation and filtering social information for German clients, with grievance systems that involve workers only minimally.</p>	<p>Face constant evaluation and bear most system costs (audits, upgrades, losses from rejections or price cuts). They finance the "responsibility" supermarkets showcase but have no influence over how incidents are interpreted or how financial impacts are allocated, which fall overwhelmingly on producers in Huelva.</p>

4. Case study: Morocco - United Kingdom value chain

Analysis of human rights, CSR and due diligence policies of selected supermarkets

Overview

This section analyses corporate documents from seven UK supermarkets involved in the Morocco-United Kingdom strawberry supply chain that set out their human rights, CSR and HRDD policies, and integrates insights from a focus group held with representatives from five UK supermarkets. The analysis consolidates corporate modern slavery and human rights statements, supplier codes, governance arrangements and HRDD practices in agricultural value chains.

Across the documents, supermarkets formally commit to respect for internationally recognised standards, with policies aligned to the International Bill of Human Rights, the International Labour Organization (ILO) core conventions, the UNGPs on Business and Human Rights and, in supplier codes, requirements mirroring the ETI (Ethical Trade Initiative) Base Code. Board level approval of modern slavery statements and formal oversight through sustainability or corporate responsibility committees are emphasised, alongside cross functional human rights governance and periodic policy review. These arrangements embed a tone from the top, placing human rights on enterprise risk registers and mandating senior accountability for implementation.

The corporate documents and focus group contributions also reflect a progressive formalisation of human rights governance over time, particularly following the introduction of transparency obligations in 2015, and describe efforts to strengthen audit quality and to bring human rights expertise closer to sourcing regions. Together, these elements indicate a shift from head office only approaches towards more regionally grounded oversight and growing specialisation.

Risk identification and prioritisation

The policy documents describe risk-based HRDD processes that integrate geographic, sectoral and workforce indicators, supported by tools such as Sedex (Supplier Ethical Data Exchange) risk ratings and Food Network for Ethical Trade indices, and refined through saliency assessments. Seasonal and migrant labour in labour-intensive agriculture is consistently signalled as higher risk. Certain fresh produce, including berries, appears among high-risk product categories prioritised for deeper assessment; in parallel, dedicated country or commodity mapping informs where enhanced due diligence is required. Some supermarkets augment desk-based tools with field teams and stakeholder input to capture emerging issues and to prioritise where leverage is highest.

Interview-based insights reinforce and nuance this picture. Participants reported using combined “baseline audit” and “beyond audit” lenses, with internal country-risk ratings

drawing on third-party indices and internal intelligence. Where sourcing shifts or particular risks (for example, accommodation or gender dynamics) become more salient, collaboration has been used to develop guidance and to focus interventions. Seasonality was repeatedly identified as a structural feature that heightens vulnerability in soft-fruit chains. These observations align with the risk focus in the policy documents while highlighting how prioritisation adapts to operational realities.

Implementation and operational measures

Operationally, suppliers are required to meet codes of conduct and responsible sourcing standards covering wages, hours, child and forced labour prohibitions, non-discrimination, freedom of association and health and safety. Supplier onboarding includes ethical due diligence, Sedex registration and self-assessment; higher-risk sites undergo third-party audits (commonly SMETA (Sedex Members Ethical Trade Audit) or comparable), with corrective action plans for non-compliances and escalation protocols for severe findings. Several documents describe extending monitoring below tier one (for example, to farms or packhouses) and investing in auditor quality assurance (including witness programmes) to improve the robustness of findings. Supermarkets also integrate human-rights checks into routine technical visits through mobile reporting tools, and they provide capacity-building for buyers and suppliers, frequently via partnerships (e.g., Stronger Together, ETI, responsible recruitment toolkits).

The interview material complements these measures with practice-level insights. Participants discussed the role of auditor competence and calibration, including additional training for context-specific issues, and described the practical limits of short-duration audits in eliciting worker perspectives. They also emphasised “beyond audit” strategies, worker-voice technologies, facilitation by trusted local partners, and collaborative guidance (e.g., on accommodation), to address sensitive issues not easily surfaced through compliance checks alone. These accounts are consistent with corporate commitments to move beyond a purely compliance-oriented model.

Monitoring, traceability and transparency

Monitoring is portrayed as a continuous process combining independent audits, data dashboards (e.g., Sedex workflows), worker feedback channels and periodic reporting to governance forums. Transparency initiatives include publishing supplier lists (beyond tier one for selected high-risk categories) and participation in sectoral information-sharing networks designed to identify and disrupt severe exploitation. Some reports include quantitative disclosures on audit coverage, case handling and remediation progress, alongside efforts to map deeper tiers of agricultural supply chains.

Interviewees noted the usefulness of external hotlines in some jurisdictions and the practical challenges of enabling effective worker reporting where language barriers and seasonality complicate access and trust. These reflections support the documents’ focus on transparency and on strengthening traceability and monitoring beyond first-tier suppliers.

Grievance and remedy mechanisms

Policy documents consistently describe multi-channel grievance architectures that extend to supply-chain workers, combining site-level procedures with independent hotlines and whistleblowing services. Incident management processes set out investigation, escalation and remediation pathways, with an emphasis on survivor-centred remedy (e.g., reimbursement of recruitment fees, wage restitution) and on corrective action over termination, while retaining the option of responsible exit where improvement is not forthcoming. Supermarkets also report collaboration to strengthen grievance access in high-risk contexts and to improve recruitment practices (including the Employer Pays Principle).

Interviewees echoed the importance of ensuring that mechanisms are not only present but effective, highlighting the difference between formal channels and trusted, usable ones. Reported challenges include worker awareness, confidence and the complexity of multiple overlapping systems across short seasons. Participants pointed to supplier capacity-building and industry collaboration as levers to improve mechanism quality and uptake. These insights are consistent with the documents' emphasis on remedy and continuous improvement.

Regional and sectoral focus: Morocco-United Kingdom strawberry supply chain

The corporate documents do not contain a dedicated, named programme for the Morocco-United Kingdom strawberry chain; rather, they indicate that agricultural soft-fruit risks are addressed through general HRDD systems and, in some cases, commodity- or region-specific initiatives in neighbouring production hubs. Examples in the corpus include gender-focused assessments in berry supply chains, pre-departure worker-rights information tools for seasonal migrants (including those from Morocco), and cross-regional civil-society networks designed to connect origin and destination actors on ethical recruitment and grievance access. One analysis notes that strengthened farm-level certification requirements in higher-risk sourcing regions, including Morocco, are being used as conditions of supply, with social modules relevant to labour standards.

Interviewees described seasonal dynamics, collaborative development of guidance (for example, on worker accommodation) and efforts to engage workers during site visits, where feasible, through independent and confidential conversations. These themes complement the policy materials' emphasis on risk-led, collaborative and worker-centred approaches, while underscoring the operational complexity of implementing them consistently.

Impacts on the labour conditions of farm workers - Stakeholder Perspectives (agents, suppliers and growers)

Overview

This section analyses stakeholder perspectives on how supermarkets' CSR and HRDD frameworks, together with the commercial relationships that accompany them, shape working and living conditions in the strawberry value chain between Morocco and the UK. It

draws on interviews with two independent experts on the Moroccan strawberry sector, with no corporate affiliation, as well as two cooperative suppliers and four growers, and reflects their assessments of supermarket codes of conduct, audit and certification requirements, buyer expectations and grievance channels. The analysis focuses on how these actors perceive the coherence between declared CSR and HRDD commitments and actual sourcing practices, including price setting, order management and the allocation of risks along the chain.

Agents

From the agent's vantage point, retail requirements (certifications, minimum pay, regulated hours, basic OHS) exert preventive pressure intended to pre-empt abuse. Heightened reputational sensitivity has incentivised some buyers to request more social data and participate in improvement initiatives. At the same time, commercial practices, last-minute orders, sudden price changes and slow payments, translate into labour intensification and unpaid overtime, particularly during harvest peaks when daily wages do not adjust to hours worked. The agent characterises a two-tier reality: larger, export-focused farms experience modest improvements under scrutiny, while smaller or indirect suppliers can persist with poor practices with limited oversight. Announced audits and contingent enforcement dilute accountability when supply security is prioritised.

Suppliers

Suppliers describe stringent internal controls focused on fruit quality, volume and food safety. Sanctions and expulsions are reported for quality infractions, whereas labour violations are treated as the grower's internal matter unless quality is compromised. Several interviewees reported that audit processes can be stage-managed: inspections are pre-announced, farms are prepared and selected for visits, and sensitive issues or workers are kept out of sight on audit days. Allegations of questionable relationships with local audit providers and selective showcasing of "presentable" farms appear, alongside reports of occasional logistical supports (e.g., safe transport for certain workers) driven primarily by quality or hygiene considerations rather than by a worker-rights agenda. Oversight over field-level supervisors and informal labour contractors is largely absent, leaving day-to-day treatment of workers unmonitored.

Growers

Growers openly report dependence on temporary seasonal labour, frequently without formal contracts. Reasons given include the perceived cost of formalisation (payroll taxes, social security contributions) and claims that some workers prefer informality to avoid losing welfare benefits; whatever the rationale, the result is exclusion from legal protections. Flat day rates prevail, with long peak-season hours and quota systems that extend working days without overtime. Repetitive, physically demanding work leads to musculoskeletal strain, with limited recourse for rest or ergonomic support. Some growers describe minor mitigations (e.g., adjusting schedules during extreme heat) for pragmatic retention reasons rather than adherence to standards. Audits and buyer visits are widely viewed as theatrical,

focused on hygiene and infrastructure rather than hours or pay; smaller farms report receiving few, if any, inspections. Some growers exit export channels due to compliance and payment frustrations, moving to less regulated markets with minimal social requirements.

Comparative Matrix: Stakeholder Impacts on Farm Labour Conditions and OHS (Morocco-United Kingdom)

Table 3: Comparative Matrix: Stakeholder Impacts on Farm Labour Conditions and OHS (Morocco-United Kingdom)

Theme	Agents (independent experts - observer role)	Suppliers / Importers (intermediary companies)	Growers (farm owners / producer-exporters)
Audit Oversight and Compliance	The agents notes that, in general, audits and standards are applied in a formal manner, but because they are pre-announced and superficial, their effectiveness is significantly reduced. They observe that audits tend to focus on documentation and appearance rather than on worker engagement, which, even if unintentionally, facilitates the concealment of structural problems.	Actively stage audits with farms to hide real conditions. Warn producers in advance, select compliant farms for visits, and temporarily remove non-compliant practices or workers.	Treat audits as one-day theatre. Make temporary cosmetic changes (cleaning, PPE, scripted worker responses) and then return to usual practices.
Purchasing and Order Pressures	Last-minute orders, price cuts, and slow payments push farms into unpaid overtime and cost-cutting. Reject shipments without compensation, increasing pressure.	Pass market pressures directly to producers. Enforce strict grading and high rejection rates, reduce payments through deductions, and provide no	Intensify labour to meet fluctuating orders: long hours without overtime, high quotas, informal hiring during peaks. Some leave export markets to avoid strict requirements.

		incentives for better labour practices.	
Labour Formalisation and Contracts	They consider that formal contracts and legal wages are required <i>on paper</i> , but enforcement is weak. They note that sourcing continues even under informal conditions when supply reliability is prioritised.	Include labour clauses in membership contracts but do not monitor or sanction violations. Labour requirements remain symbolic.	Favour informal labour to reduce costs. Workers often lack contracts, social security, and legal protections. Slight wage increases appear due to labour shortages, but jobs remain informal.
Occupational Health and Safety (OHS)	Expect basic OHS on paper but overlook deficiencies when supply is at risk. Checklist approach focuses on visible items, not deeper risks (ergonomics, heat stress).	Enforce OHS only when it affects product quality (pesticides, hygiene). Neglect worker centred OHS such as rest, shade, or ergonomic protection.	Invest minimally in worker safety unless required externally. PPE, sanitation, and rest areas are often absent except during audits; chronic injuries are treated as workers' personal issues.
Reputational Pressure and Response	They consider that supermarkets react mainly when risks become public. Media or NGO exposés trigger warnings or supplier removal. They note that preventive action depends heavily on the external visibility of the issue.	Some stakeholders perceived cooperatives as prioritising reputational protection. Handle issues privately, apply only mild sanctions, and reassure buyers with superficial fixes.	Stakeholder described uneven preventive action: some exporters were seen as taking limited steps mainly to reduce reputational exposure; some smaller producers were described as facing less pressure to comply. Some switch to markets with fewer requirements.

5. Benchmarking the structure and effectiveness of CSR measures, due diligence processes, etc. across both value chains

The following section presents a structured benchmarking exercise between the two value chains analysed, with the aim of identifying how their social, labour and HRDD practices are configured across their different links. To this end, a comparative table has been developed that synthesizes the information available across nine key dimensions, ranging from audits and purchasing practices to worker vulnerability and power distribution, and assigns a level of residual risk (low, medium or high) to each category and each chain. This approach enables a systematic visualization, aligned with HRDD frameworks, of the areas where the main social risks are concentrated, as well as those in which current management instruments are insufficient or exhibit greater robustness.

Comparative benchmarking table

Table 4: Comparative benchmarking table between both value chains

Category	Chain A: Huelva-Germany	Chain B: Morocco-United Kingdom	Synthetic comparison	Risk level (Low / Medium / High)
Auditing and compliance	Dense architecture based on agricultural and social certifications (GLOBALG.A.P., social modules, environmental modules, etc.) also driven by the supply chain law of the destination country. Frequent audits but often formal and focused on paperwork. Uneven audit quality depending on the farm and the size of the producer. More solid coverage in integrated companies and more limited for small producers.	Configuration supported by GLOBALG.A.P. and SMETA audits, with additional requirements (trainings, platforms). Some buyers try to make audits deeper (peak season, lists of approved auditors), but in practice they are staged: announced visits, showcase farms, temporary removal of women workers without a contract. Audit costs are high for small producers.	In both chains there is a sophisticated standards architecture, but with a clear gap between design and practice. Huelva-Germany relies more on integrated modules and a legal obligation. Morocco-United Kingdom shows more experimentation with audit design, but also more evidence of staged audits and exclusion of problematic farms from real scrutiny.	<p>Chain A: Medium risk.</p> <p>There is a relatively robust regulatory and certification framework, but the quality of audits and uneven coverage leave important risks undetected.</p> <p>Chain B: Medium risk.</p> <p>There is also a consolidated standards structure, but staged audits and strong segmentation between showcase farms and the rest prevent the system from effectively controlling underlying risks.</p>
Purchasing practices and commercial conditions	Chain strongly oriented toward price, with strict technical and cosmetic standards and rejection rules that shift almost	Slightly higher base prices, but combined with frequent competitive bidding between	In both chains, purchasing practices are a structural factor of risk. They externalise commercial risk to producers	<p>Chain A: High risk.</p> <p>The combination of low prices, strict standards and</p>

Category	Chain A: Huelva-Germany	Chain B: Morocco-United Kingdom	Synthetic comparison	Risk level (Low / Medium / High)
	all commercial risk to producers. Rigid logistics, narrow delivery windows and last-minute orders generate constant reorganisation of shifts, intensification of work rhythms and pressure over labour conditions.	suppliers, short contracts, reclassification of fruit at destination, discounts and late payments. Last minute orders and abrupt changes in conditions intensify working hours and encourage cost cutting strategies, including labour informality, especially in small and medium sized farms.	and, in cascade, to workers. The UK chain offers somewhat more technical feedback, but introduces more volatility. The German chain is more rigid and based on zero tolerance. In both cases, commercial logic is not compatible with internalising the costs of decent work.	rejection policies with little cost for the buyer creates strong incentives to adjust through labour conditions and OHS pressure. Chain B: High risk. Despite slightly higher prices, contractual volatility, discounts and late payments generate similar pressure, with strong incentives for informality and labour cost compression.
Labour formalisation	The labour framework of the producing country and certification requirements have increased the use of formal contracts, social security registration and hour tracking in farms linked to large distribution. Gaps persist between formal documentation and real working hours, the use	In large farms and cooperatives oriented toward export, progress has been made in formalisation (contracts, social security), but informality is still very frequent, especially among seasonal women workers. Social security	The Huelva-Germany chain rests on a stronger legal base and seems to have achieved more widespread formalisation on paper, although there are doubts about correspondence with real practice. In Morocco-United Kingdom, formalisation has improved in export segments, but coexists with	Chain A: Medium risk. There is relevant legal formalisation, but seasonality and adjustment practices (extra hours, subcontracting) maintain a significant risk of material non compliance.

Category	Chain A: Huelva-Germany	Chain B: Morocco-United Kingdom	Synthetic comparison	Risk level (Low / Medium / High)
	of subcontracting and limited stability of seasonal employment.	contribution costs and incentives within the social protection system led some women to avoid formalisation. Dual regime: a formalised core and a broad informal periphery.	very widespread structural informality.	<p>Chain B: High risk.</p> <p>The persistence of work without contracts, grey areas linked to social protection and the dual regime generate a high risk of violations of basic labour rights.</p>
Occupational health and safety (OHS)	<p>OHS is integrated into national laws and certification schemes: training, basic requirements on housing, transport, etc. However, pressure from cutting windows and logistics generates intense work rhythms, long shifts and physical overload. The agenda of buyers prioritises environmental issues and food safety more than social and worker centred OHS.</p>	<p>OHS is approached mainly from food safety (pesticides, hygiene), with less attention to ergonomics, fatigue or heat stress. Long working days, demanding quotas and poor transport conditions generate health problems that rarely become a central focus of audits. There are punctual improvements (for example in transport) driven by some buyers,</p>	<p>Relatively, the Spanish German chain benefits from a broader OHS legal and certification framework, although implementation gaps appear during peak campaign periods. In the Morocco-United Kingdom chain, worker centred OHS is weaker and depends on punctual initiatives rather than a consistent system.</p>	<p>Chain A: Medium risk.</p> <p>There are basic rules and controls, but campaign intensity and the priority given to other topics (environment, product quality) leave important risks insufficiently addressed.</p> <p>Chain B: High risk.</p> <p>The focus is almost exclusively on ensuring the product is safe for consumers, with much less attention to working</p>

Category	Chain A: Huelva-Germany	Chain B: Morocco-United Kingdom	Synthetic comparison	Risk level (Low / Medium / High)
		but not a systematic approach.		conditions such as ergonomics, heat or transport. This keeps worker OHS risks high.
Reputational dynamics and risk response	Supply chain legislation requires demonstrating due diligence processes and risk management. Reputational response has been most visible in environmental issues. In social issues, the logic is mainly certification and documentary compliance. Participation in multi stakeholder forums by some supermarkets is seen as positive with potential for change. The capacity to respond to labour risks depends largely on audits and occasional public pressure.	The MSA and strong media pressure drive sophisticated reporting systems, participation in collaborative platforms and reactive responses to scandals (more audits, visits, criteria adjustments). However, enforcement is selective and depends on market context (stricter when there is abundant supply, more flexible when supply is tight).	The analysis suggests that CSR and HRDD are often perceived and used as reputational management tools. The Morocco-United Kingdom chain shows a greater density of collaborative initiatives and stronger reaction capacity in response to allegations, while the Huelva-Germany chain relies more on legal architecture and certification. In neither case does reputational response alone ensure structural improvements in labour conditions.	<p>Chain A: Medium risk.</p> <p>Legal obligation and formal mechanisms reduce the risk of total inaction, but limited focus on social issues leaves important risks unaddressed.</p> <p>Chain B: Medium risk.</p> <p>Reaction capacity and collaborative initiatives reduce some risks, but selective and reactive application leaves a significant residual risk, especially without changes in purchasing practices.</p>
CSR / HRDD design and implementation	Broad corporate commitments to human rights, specific governance structures and a	Human rights and modern slavery policies, supplier codes, risk based HRDD	In both cases there is a relatively advanced design of CSR and HRDD at the corporate	Chain A: Medium risk.

Category	Chain A: Huelva-Germany	Chain B: Morocco-United Kingdom	Synthetic comparison	Risk level (Low / Medium / High)
	human rights impact assessment focused on the Huelva-Germany chain, with an action plan covering housing, worker voice and commercial practices (for example reducing last minute orders, transparency on labour cost structures). The degree of full implementation is still limited.	processes and tools beyond auditing (worker voice, local partners, training). However, there is no specific programme for the Morocco-United Kingdom chain, and actual coverage is uneven depending on region and farm type.	level. The main difference is that Chain A has a legal obligation and a chain specific human rights assessment, while Chain B depends on voluntary frameworks and broader regional programmes. The translation of these frameworks into operational improvements on farms remains partial in both chains.	Design and instruments are relatively advanced. Residual risks come from the gap between plans and practice, not from lack of framework. Chain B: High risk. Voluntary architecture is sophisticated, but the lack of a chain specific programme and uneven implementation leave a significant risk that structural problems remain unaddressed.
Vulnerability of migrant and seasonal workers	High dependence on migrant and seasonal labour, with recognised risks (housing, gender, campaign intensity). Employer linked housing and transport increase dependence. Although the legal framework provides formal rights, migration status, language	Very high vulnerability of seasonal workers: low wages, frequent informality, strong dependence on cooperatives and employers for access to work, transport and in some cases housing.	Both chains rely on highly replaceable, dependent labour with little voice. Chain A has a stronger legal framework but faces similar structural limits in reducing vulnerability. Chain B shows some mitigation initiatives but coexists with	Chain A: High risk. Despite formal rights and some commitments, the combination of migration status, seasonality and dependence on employer linked housing and

Category	Chain A: Huelva-Germany	Chain B: Morocco-United Kingdom	Synthetic comparison	Risk level (Low / Medium / High)
	barriers and fear of losing employment or permits limit effective exercise of rights and use of complaint channels.	Gender and social protection factors interact in a way that discourages formalisation and increases exposure to abuse.	widespread informality and precariousness.	transport creates strong structural vulnerability. Chain B: High risk. Widespread informality, dependence on cooperatives and disincentives for formalisation create very high vulnerability. Current instruments only partially mitigate risks for some groups.
Distribution of power and value	Price setting, standards and calendars are concentrated in supermarkets. Producers and intermediaries bear certification costs, improvement investments and rejection risks. Small farms are dependent on cooperatives and have very limited margins. There are few mechanisms to share risks or	Supermarkets and cooperatives or exporters in Morocco share asymmetric power over small producers. They control inputs, access to market and commercial conditions. Farmers face discounts, delays, debt and extremely limited negotiation capacity.	In both chains, governance is clearly buyer driven and costs and risks are pushed downward. Differences lie mainly in commercial style (strict rules versus frequent changes) rather than structure. There are no meaningful mechanisms to share risks or explicitly reward social compliance.	Chain A: High risk. The concentration of power and lack of risk sharing mechanisms make it likely that CSR requirements translate into pressure on wages, work rhythms and employment stability. Chain B: High risk.

Category	Chain A: Huelva-Germany	Chain B: Morocco-United Kingdom	Synthetic comparison	Risk level (Low / Medium / High)
	rebalance value toward producers.	Social compliance costs are ultimately transferred to producers and workers.		The combination of concentrated power in supermarkets and cooperatives and lack of rebalancing tools creates a very high structural risk that the costs of responsibility fall on workers.

Comparative analysis

In general terms, both chains have a developed formal design of CSR and human rights due diligence, but with important structural limitations. The Huelva-Germany chain is grounded in a strong legal framework (LkSG and the future CSDDD) and in a specific impact assessment (carried out by one single supermarket out of the five analysed) that has generated a (limited) action plan for the territory, while the Morocco-United Kingdom chain rests on a sophisticated voluntary framework (Sedex/SMETA, sectoral networks) driven by the MSA and by high sensitivity to reputational risk.

Areas where Chain A is relatively better positioned include labour formalisation, the regulatory anchoring and, to some extent, OHS. The Spanish legal context requires written contracts, social security registration and compliance with occupational risk prevention rules, which, combined with audits and HRDD, has strengthened documentary formalisation in farms linked to the German market. The LkSG sets out clear obligations on risk management, preventive measures and grievance mechanisms, and a specific impact assessment for Huelva has made it possible to identify risks in housing, gender and labour relations, proposing actions such as reducing last minute orders and improving transparency on wage cost structures. Although implementation is far from complete, Chain A has a governance structure that, at least in theory, makes it easier to demand improvements.

Areas where Chain B shows a relative advantage are found in reputational dynamics, the sophistication of collaborative tools and some aspects of auditing. British supermarkets have been pioneers in creating and using platforms such as Sedex, SMETA protocols and pre-competitive networks to discuss social risks, adjust the content of audits (for example, by giving more weight to worker transport) and develop “beyond auditing” tools, such as worker voice technologies or projects on housing. Rapid reaction to media reports and NGO allegations, through new visits, adjusted requirements and intensified scrutiny, introduces more dynamic reputational mechanisms than those observed so far in the German chain, which is more focused on certification and formal compliance with the law.

However, when purchasing practices and the distribution of power are examined, the differences between the chains decrease considerably. In both cases, commercial logic (price, cosmetic or technical standards, risk of rejection) directly limits the effectiveness of CSR and HRDD. In Huelva-Germany, low prices, high quality demands and rejection clauses with little cost for the buyer shift risk to producers, who respond by intensifying work rhythms and seeking forms of labour flexibility that often push regulatory limits. In Morocco-United Kingdom, the combination of slightly higher prices with continuous competition between suppliers, frequent changes in purchasing conditions, reclassification of fruit at destination and late payments generates high uncertainty and encourages informality and saving on labour costs, especially in small and medium sized farms. Sometimes these pressures are strong enough for some producers to decide to leave the English market and focus on the Moroccan market, which is much less controlled in social terms.

The distribution of power and value is clearly asymmetric in both chains. Supermarkets define standards, certifications and calendars, while cooperatives and exporters translate

and amplify these demands but can rarely renegotiate the underlying economic and commercial logic. In Huelva, large integrated companies can absorb the administrative cost of “responsibility”, while small farms are subordinated to cooperatives or excluded from the German circuit. In Morocco, cooperatives not only intermediate sales but also control inputs, varieties and access to market, subtracting their costs from the fruit delivered and filtering which farms are shown to British buyers. Small producers describe situations of indebtedness and unilateral discounts that leave them with very little room for manoeuvre. In both cases, the costs of social compliance are mainly internalised by the weakest links and passed down to workers.

With regard to the vulnerability of migrant and seasonal workers, structural patterns emerge that are common to both chains. Both rely on seasonal labour that is highly dependent on the employer for housing and transport, subject to intense work rhythms and with very limited influence over decisions in the chain. In Morocco-United Kingdom, informality, low wages and incentives not to formalise (in order not to lose social benefits) reinforce the fragility of women workers, despite the progress achieved in some export segments. In Huelva-Germany, the legal framework offers greater formal guarantees, but the vulnerable position associated with migration status, dependence on the employer for housing and extreme seasonality limits the effective exercise of rights and the use of corporate grievance mechanisms.

Despite these limitations, it is possible to identify good practices that could be transferred between chains:

1. From Huelva-Germany to Morocco-United Kingdom, carrying out specific impact assessments in the strawberry sector, with action plans that include adjustments in purchasing practices, could help to better align formal commitments with the reality of Moroccan farms.
2. From Morocco-United Kingdom to Huelva-Germany, requiring audits during peak season and investing in training and calibration of auditors so that they can detect specific risks (transport, housing, gender) could improve the quality of social verification in Huelva, which is currently perceived as very document based.
3. Greater integration of HRDD into binding legal frameworks (such as the LkSG or the future CSDDD) offers a useful reference for the British context, which is currently limited to transparency obligations without substantive enforceability.

Finally, there are structural bottlenecks that will not be resolved by “more audits”:

1. Business models based on low prices, strict cosmetic standards and high volumes imply, by design, very limited margins for producers, which makes it difficult to incorporate the costs of living wages, adequate housing and rest time into the price of the fruit.
2. Fragmentation and competition between certification schemes (LEAF vs SPRING, SMETA vs GRASP/BSCI) generate duplication and additional costs without necessarily

improving outcomes for workers, and they restrict producers' ability to redirect their production to the market that offers the best remuneration at any given time.

3. The intermediation of cooperatives and exporting companies, which filter information towards supermarkets and sometimes stage audits, limits visibility of the real conditions at the base of the production chain and weakens accountability towards workers.
4. The combination of extreme seasonality and social protection frameworks which, in practice, discourage formalisation (as in the Moroccan case) produces pockets of informality that cannot be corrected solely through private standards.
5. The weak articulation of workers' voice in the governance of the chains, beyond their participation as interviewees in audits, prevents CSR and HRDD mechanisms from evolving towards models that are genuinely centred on affected people.

In summary, both cases show chains with relatively sophisticated CSR and HRDD instruments at the top, but trapped in commercial and power structures that stakeholders and prior research suggest can limit transformative capacity. The comparison points to the need to move from a logic focused on verification and reputational management to one that explicitly addresses prices, risk sharing and the effective participation of workers and producers in defining the rules of the game.

6. Conclusions, recommendations and contribution to SafeHabitus project

Conclusions

Taken together, the analysis of the two strawberry value chains shows that CSR and HRDD frameworks, in their current configuration, are necessary but clearly insufficient instruments to ensure decent work in export-oriented agricultural contexts that are strongly driven by large-scale retail. These frameworks have contributed to the development of new language, regulatory architectures and procedures, and have even prompted concrete improvements in areas such as contract formalisation, the codification of certain health and safety obligations, or the creation of formal complaint channels. However, these advances rest on an economic and power structure that remains practically intact and continues to shift risk towards the bottom of the chain and structural vulnerability onto migrant and seasonal workers.

Evidence collected in Huelva and in Morocco's producing regions points to a recurrent pattern: the proliferation of codes of conduct, social audits, certifications and compliance statements does not systematically translate into verifiable changes in the organisation of work, working hours, health protection, housing quality or the real capacity of workers to

claim their rights without fear of reprisals. In practice, much of the CSR and HRDD architecture tends to operate as a reputational risk management and documentary compliance mechanism that responds to regulatory and public-opinion pressures rather than as an instrument capable of transforming power relations along the chain and redistributing risks and margins more equitably.

The comparison between the Huelva-Germany chain and the Morocco-United Kingdom chain reinforces this reading. In the first case, the existence of a binding due diligence framework for companies headquartered in Germany has driven greater formalisation of risk management systems, as well as more detailed mapping of the supplier base and of the risks associated with seasonal work and employer-provided accommodation. In the second, the transparency- and self-reporting-centred approach of the MSA has encouraged the production of reports and commitments, but with a much more limited impact on business practices and on conditions at origin. However, in neither case can it be said that the existing regulatory framework has substantively altered the power asymmetries between supermarkets, intermediaries, producers and workers.

The findings also show that CSR and HRDD frameworks have tended to focus on the existence of policies, protocols and grievance mechanisms rather than on actual outcomes for workers. What is easily auditable and recordable is prioritised over what is more difficult to measure but more relevant from a rights perspective: effective working and rest time, possibilities for organising collectively, the capacity to refuse abusive conditions, or real scope for decision-making over one's own migration project. In this sense, the emphasis on documentary compliance, risk assessment on paper and pre-announced audits has proved insufficient to uncover entrenched practices of undeclared work, unpaid overtime, discriminatory treatment or tolerance of harassment.

Furthermore, the research confirms that many of the factors that most influence labour risks are not found solely in the field or the packhouse, but in the way commercial relationships are structured along the chain. Tight prices, intense competition between suppliers and constant pressure to respond to the requirements of large-scale retail create a context in which some economic actors choose to protect their position by pushing tensions down onto the labour base. This translates, all too often, into work intensification, concentration of physically demanding tasks in the weakest links, widespread use of precarious or overcrowded accommodation and the use of migrant workers as easily replaceable labour. These decisions are not inevitable, but rather the result of specific business strategies which, if not confronted through effective regulation, inspection and collective organising, will continue to reproduce violations of rights. Although purchasing practices and quality demands exert significant pressure on producers, these structural dynamics do not negate their legal responsibilities. Labour rights violations cannot be justified by reference to market constraints, as employers remain accountable for upholding statutory standards.

At the institutional level, the cases analysed also reveal the limits of a model that rests on the idea that the lead company can, by itself, correct market failures and fill the gaps in public regulation. The role of labour, inspection, housing and migration authorities in Spain and

Morocco is decisive in defining the floor of rights below which competition is not permitted. Likewise, the way in which the German supply chain legislation, the new European Due Diligence Directive and other rules related to unfair trading practices are implemented will shape the extent to which human rights obligations move beyond the realm of CSR and become a basic condition for operating in the European market. If these frameworks are emptied of substance through broad exemptions, weak oversight or merely symbolic sanctions, their capacity to drive material change in high-risk agricultural sectors will be very limited.

Recommendations

Based on the evidence produced by the report, a series of recommendations is proposed:

To supermarkets:

1- Commit to respecting labour and human rights across the supply chain and implement impact-driven systems.

Supermarkets should make a clear commitment and operationalise it through robust, impact-oriented due diligence that identifies and mitigates risks, aligns purchasing practices so they do not incentivise harm, and ensures effective grievance and remediation mechanisms, supported by transparency on salient risks and corrective actions.

2- Pay fair prices instead of imposing unilateral conditions on producers.

Agree on prices that reflect the real costs of sustainable production and decent work, rather than dictating prices and conditions from a position of market power.

3- Integrate human rights into corporate management and internal incentive systems.

Make the prevention and remediation of violations a central responsibility of company leadership. This requires due diligence systems to identify risks and actual cases, effective remedy measures, and internal incentives (for example, in purchasing) that are aligned with clear social objectives rather than solely with price, volume and fruit quality. Audits cannot be the only means of verifying conditions on farms, given the deficiencies these audits present.

4- Increase transparency and accountability in the supply chain.

Regularly publish a list of relevant suppliers, together with aggregated information on identified risks and measures taken.

5- Contribute to a fairer food system by supporting regional, organic and small-scale farming.

Orient purchasing policies toward strengthening regional, organic and small-scale farming operations through stable contracts and fairer commercial conditions, instead of relying increasingly on industrialized agriculture.

To the EU:

1- Adopt an effective EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (EU CSDDD).

Adopt an EU CSDDD with a broad scope, strong enforcement mechanisms and clear obligations on companies for their entire supply chains inside and outside the EU.

2- Guarantee access to legal protection and remedies for affected persons.

Ensure that the EU CSDDD grants persons impacted by exploitation in supply chains effective access to justice, including remedies to obtain compensation for damages, with alleviated burdens of proof for plaintiffs.

3- Require companies to adapt their sourcing and purchasing policies.

Include explicit obligations for companies to adjust their sourcing and purchasing practices in order to improve the conditions for fair wages and decent working conditions throughout their supply chains.

4- Ensure meaningful rights-holder engagement throughout HREDD processes.

Include clear requirements for companies to conduct ongoing, safe and meaningful engagement with workers, communities and other rights holders at all stages of HREDD, from risk identification to the design and monitoring of preventive and mitigating measures and grievance mechanisms.

5- Make HREDD explicitly gender responsive.

Require companies to integrate a gender-responsive approach into HREDD, including gender analysis, sex-disaggregated data and measures and grievance mechanisms that address gender-specific risks and barriers, particularly for migrant and seasonal women workers.

6- Mandate the payment of living wages from the base of the supply chain.

Establish, within the EU CSDDD, a clear requirement that companies ensure the payment of living wages, starting with workers at the base of agricultural and food supply chains.

Contribution to SafeHabitus Work Programme and Expected Outcomes

This report directly fulfils the objectives of Task 5.3 within Work Package 5, which applies a 'Farm to Fork' perspective to assess the potential of CSR initiatives to improve labour conditions in agricultural value chains. The comparative analysis of two strawberry chains, Huelva-Germany and Morocco-United Kingdom, documents the enabling conditions for market developments that support ethical working conditions, as set out in the SafeHabitus Grant Agreement.

The findings contribute to the four Expected Outcomes of the SafeHabitus project. With regard to the first outcome, on enhanced understanding and awareness, the comparative analysis provides policymakers, farmers' organisations, trade unions and health authorities with detailed evidence on how CSR and HRDD frameworks operate in practice within supermarket-led agricultural chains. The research documents how commercial pressures (pricing strategies, cosmetic standards and just-in-time logistics) interact with formal social

compliance systems to shape actual working conditions. This evidence base deepens understanding of the structural factors that perpetuate OHS risks and labour vulnerabilities among migrant and seasonal workers, with implications for workforce attraction and retention and, by extension, for the long-term viability of European food production.

With regard to the second outcome, on improved policy and governance frameworks, the benchmarking exercise identifies governance gaps and structural bottlenecks that limit the effectiveness of current regulatory approaches. The comparison between Germany's binding due diligence regime and the UK's transparency-based framework provides an empirical foundation for assessing different regulatory models. The recommendations addressed to the EU, strengthening the CSDDD, mandating living wages and requiring alignment of purchasing practices with HRDD obligations, offer concrete inputs for improved policy frameworks at European and national levels.

With regard to the third outcome, on wider use of CSR innovations, the analysis identifies transferable good practices between the two chains, including chain-specific human rights impact assessments, peak-season audit protocols, worker voice mechanisms and collaborative initiatives on accommodation standards. By documenting what works and what remains superficial, the research provides a basis for farm businesses and value chain actors to adopt more effective CSR approaches that move beyond documentary compliance towards genuine improvements in working conditions.

With regard to the fourth outcome, on improved health, safety and labour conditions, the findings demonstrate that while CSR and HRDD frameworks have contributed to increased formalisation of employment relationships and codification of OHS requirements, these gains remain fragile and unevenly distributed. The research identifies the conditions under which such frameworks can deliver substantive improvements, notably when binding legal obligations are combined with reformed purchasing practices, meaningful worker participation and effective grievance mechanisms with access to remedy. These insights support the development of bottom-up initiatives and inform the design of more effective policy interventions.

The research also responds to the 2023 European Economic and Social Committee recommendation for studies examining the food value chain and the potential for reputational mechanisms to improve conditions for migrant workers, a call that SafeHabitus has been addressing through its programme of policy seminars and stakeholder engagement.

Linkages to subsequent SafeHabitus tasks

The findings of this report inform subsequent activities within Work Package 5 and the broader SafeHabitus work programme. Task 5.4, which examines the experiences of intra-EU and extra-EU mobile workers in agricultural settings, including those originating from Morocco and Romania, builds on the structural analysis presented here to assess how CSR

and HRDD frameworks are experienced by workers themselves. The documentation of governance gaps, audit limitations and barriers to effective grievance access provides essential context for interpreting worker testimonies and identifying where formal protections fail to translate into lived improvements.

Task 5.5, which focuses on developing ethical trade governance structures, draws directly on the Morocco-United Kingdom case study. The analysis of UK supermarkets' collaborative platforms, multi-stakeholder initiatives and 'beyond audit' approaches offers a template for the development of similar structures within the Spanish Community of Practice. The benchmarking matrix identifying relative strengths and weaknesses of each chain provides an evidence base for prioritising interventions and designing governance arrangements that address the structural bottlenecks documented here, particularly the misalignment between CSR commitments and purchasing practices.

The research findings will also be presented at the Work Package 6 Policy Seminar on 27 January 2026. The evidence on regulatory effectiveness, the comparative assessment of binding versus transparency-based frameworks, and the identification of persistent structural barriers to decent work in supermarket-led agricultural chains will inform policy dialogue with European institutions, Member State authorities and social partners. The recommendations to supermarkets and the EU presented in this section provide a starting point for these discussions, while the detailed findings on audit quality, grievance mechanism effectiveness and the distribution of power and value along the chains offer material for developing actionable policy tools that can improve health, safety and labour conditions for farmers and farm workers across the EU.

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